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INFLAMMATORY CHANGES IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF PERINATAL DISORDERS IN COVID-19

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Summary. Savchuk R. M. **INFLAMMATORY CHANGES IN THE PATHOGENESIS OF PERINATAL DISORDERS IN COVID-19.** - *Shupyk National Healthcare University of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; e-mail: tanyakolom@gmail.com.* Systemic inflammation during pregnancy due to severe SARS-CoV-2 infection is associated with severe perinatal outcomes after exposure to a maternal cytokine storm. **The aim of the study:** to determine the role of inflammatory changes in the pathogenesis of perinatal disorders in COVID-19. **Materials and methods.** The comprehensive study included: 200 pregnant women who were hospitalized with COVID-19 during pregnancy (main group) and 50 patients who did not have COVID-19 during pregnancy (control group). The main group was divided into 2 subgroups: O1 - 50 women with adverse perinatal outcomes, O2 - 150 patients with a relatively favorable course of the gestational period. Complete blood count, biochemical indicators, individual hemostasis parameters, markers of inflammation and NK cytotoxicity were taken into account. **Results.** The inflammatory reaction of the body of pregnant women with COVID-19 and perinatal disorders is evidenced by leukocytosis and a shift in the blood formula to the left. Against the background of relative thrombocytopenia, an increase in ADP-induced platelet aggregation ($65.6 \pm 4.8\%$ vs. $50.2 \pm 5.8\%$, $p < 0.05$) and an increase in the level of D-dimer (321.6 ± 21.3 vs. 242.1 ± 20.5 ng/ml, $p < 0.05$) are observed. Destructive changes in the liver are indicated by a significant increase in transaminase levels: ALT in 84.0% (vs. 45.3%, $p < 0.05$), AST in 80.0% of patients (vs. 44.0%, $p < 0.05$). Severe COVID-19 was recorded in most patients (66.0% vs. 22.7%, $p < 0.05$), which is reflected in high levels of inflammatory markers: C-reactive protein (90.0% vs. 68.7%, $p < 0.05$), procalcitonin in half of the women (50.0% vs. 12.7%, $p < 0.05$), interleukin-6 (52.0% vs. 15.3%, $p < 0.05$), NK-cytotoxicity (24.0% vs. 6.7%, $p < 0.05$). **Conclusions.** The high activity of inflammatory processes detected in COVID-19 in patients with perinatal disorders underlies systemic vasculitic changes and defects in blood coagulation processes, which cause damage to the maternal-fetal complex.

Key words: COVID-19, pregnancy, inflammation, perinatal disorders

Реферат. Савчук Р. М. **ЗАПАЛЬНІ ЗМІНИ В ПАТОГЕНЕЗІ ПЕРИНАТАЛЬНИХ ПОРУШЕНЬ ПРИ COVID-19.** Системне запалення під час вагітності, обумовлене тяжкою інфекцією SARS-CoV-2, пов'язане з серйозними перинатальними наслідками після впливу материнського цитокінового шторму. **Мета дослідження:** визначити роль запальних змін в патогенезі перинатальних порушень при COVID-19. **Матеріали та методи.** У комплексне дослідження було включено: 200 вагітних жінок, які були госпіталізовані з COVID-19 під час вагітності (основна група), та 50 пацієток, які не мали COVID-19 під час вагітності (контрольна група). Основну групу було розділено на 2 підгрупи: O1 - 50 жінок з несприятливими перинатальними результатами, O2 - 150 пацієток з відносно сприятливим

перебігом гестаційного періоду. Враховувалися загальний аналіз крові, біохімічні показники, індивідуальні параметри гемостазу, маркери запалення та НК-цитотоксичність. **Результати.** Про запальну реакцію організму вагітних з COVID-19 та перинатальними розладами свідчить лейкоцитоз та зсув формули крові вліво. На тлі відносної тромбоцитопенії спостерігається зростання АДФ-індукованої агрегації тромбоцитів ($65,6 \pm 4,8$ % проти $50,2 \pm 5,8$ %, $p < 0,05$), зростання рівня D-димеру ($321,6 \pm 21,3$ проти $242,1 \pm 20,5$ нг/мл, $p < 0,05$). На деструктивні зміни в печінці вказує суттєве підвищення рівня трансаміназ: АЛТ у $84,0$ % (проти $45,3$ %, $p < 0,05$), АСТу $80,0$ % пацієнток (проти $44,0$ %, $p < 0,05$). Тяжкий перебіг COVID-19 зафіксовано у більшості пацієнток ($66,0$ % проти $22,7$ %, $p < 0,05$), чому відповідають високі рівні маркерів запалення: С-реактивного білка ($90,0$ % проти $68,7$ %, $p < 0,05$), прокальцитоніну половини жінок ($50,0$ % проти $12,7$ %, $p < 0,05$), інтерлейкіну-6 ($52,0$ % проти $15,3$ %, $p < 0,05$), НК-цитотоксичності ($24,0$ % проти $6,7$ %, $p < 0,05$). **Висновки.** Висока активність запальних процесів, виявлена при COVID-19 у пацієнток з перинатальними порушеннями, лежить в основі системних васкулітних змін і дефектів процесів згортання крові, які обумовлюють пошкодження материнсько-плодового комплексу.

Ключові слова: COVID-19, вагітність, запалення, перинатальні порушення.

The pandemic caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) has created an unprecedented global health crisis, affecting millions of people. COVID-19 infection often begins with flu-like symptoms but can progress to pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome, multisystem dysfunction, and death in some patients [1].

The elderly and those with chronic medical conditions are at high risk of developing complications from COVID-19. Furthermore, due to physiological and immunological adaptive changes during pregnancy, pregnant women are at higher risk of severe illness [2, 3].

Studies of patients with COVID-19 have shown elevated levels of systemic inflammatory biomarkers such as C-reactive protein (CRP), ferritin, procalcitonin, and D-dimer [4].

The vast majority of severe COVID-19 cases occur in the third trimester of pregnancy [5].

Maternal immune response, viral clearance, and ultimately perinatal outcomes may depend on the timing of infection during pregnancy [6]. The three-stage immune regulation process during pregnancy is complex [7]. Although inflammation required for blastocyst implantation is common in the first trimester of pregnancy, the second trimester promotes an anti-inflammatory T helper 2 (Th2) environment necessary for fetal growth. The immune system switches to a Th1 inflammatory state in the third trimester, which is important for labor. Because the first and third trimesters are pro-inflammatory, pregnant women infected with SARS-CoV-2 during these trimesters may be at increased risk of an exaggerated response to the virus (cytokine storm) and severe disease [8].

In addition to increased proinflammatory cytokines during T-cell lymphopenia in patients with severe COVID-19, leading to cytokine storm, multiorgan failure, and death [9], elevated levels of C-reactive protein (CRP), ferritin, and procalcitonin have been reported to be associated with severe COVID-19 in pregnant women [10].

Systemic inflammation during pregnancy is associated with serious fetal outcomes, such as fetal death, raising concerns about the immediate and long-term consequences of severe SARS-CoV-2 infection for children after exposure to a maternal cytokine storm [11].

The aim of the study: To determine the role of inflammatory changes in the pathogenesis of perinatal disorders in COVID-19.

Materials and methods. The comprehensive study included 250 pregnant women: the main group - 200 women who were hospitalized with COVID-19 during pregnancy and the control group - 50 patients who did not suffer from COVID-19 or other acute respiratory viral diseases during pregnancy. To determine the risk factors for adverse perinatal outcomes in women with COVID-19, the main group was divided into 2 parts: subgroup O1 - 50 women with adverse perinatal outcomes (fetal distress, fetal growth retardation, premature birth, severe neonatal asphyxia, perinatal death), subgroup O2 - 150 patients with a relatively favorable course of the gestational period).

A comprehensive blood test was performed on an automatic hematology machine Mindray BC-3200 by photometric and conductometric methods with venous blood samples using reagents from the manufacturer "Mindray". Biochemical blood parameters were studied on a biochemical analyzer Mindray BA-88A with reagents from the manufacturer "Mindray" with venous blood plasma samples. The study of hemostasis system parameters was carried out using screening coagulation tests on a semi-automatic coagulometer Helena C-2. Natural killer cell cytotoxicity (NK-cytotoxicity) was assessed by flow cytometry using a FACScan flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson). Interleukin-6 levels in peripheral blood were measured by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.

Statistical processing of primary data was carried out using the standard Microsoft Office Excel 2010 package and the STATISTICA 6.0 software package.

Research results and their discussion

The inflammatory reaction of the body of pregnant women with COVID-19 is evidenced by leukocytosis and a shift of the blood formula to the left (table), which is especially pronounced in patients with perinatal disorders (group O1).

Table - Changes in laboratory parameters in COVID-19 in pregnant women

Parameter	Main group, n = 200	Group O1, n = 50	Group O2, n = 150	Control, n = 50
Leukocytes, 10 ⁹ /L	12.8±1.8	15.1±1.4*#	10.1±0.7	9.7±0.8
lymphocytes, %	24.7±3.1	20.9±2.6*	27.3±2.1	29.3±2.8
monocytes, %	5.2±0.8	5.7±1.3	5.3±0.7	4.6±0.7
eosinophils, %	1.8±0.6	1.6±0.5	1.9±0.4	2.1±0.4
rod neutrophils, %	5.6±1.4	7.6±1.6*	4.6±1.5	2.9±1.4
segmented neutrophils, %	58.2±6.0	62.5±5.8	56.4±4.0	55.3±4.5
Platelets, 10 ⁹ /L	210.7±20.5	180.2±17.2*	215.3±19.1	234.5±14.2
ATA-induced platelet aggregation index, %	57.5±5.7	65.6±4.8*#	50.2±5.8	47.6±4.3
Fibrinogen, g/l	4.2±0.9	4.5±0.8	4.1±0.9	3.1±0.8
Prothrombin index, %	112.9±8.3	120.4±11.5*	107.9±9.1	92.5±7.8
APTT, s	30.2±3.1	27.5±3.1	31.1±2.8	36.3±2.6
INR	0.82 ± 0.07	0.79 ± 0.07	0.86 ± 0.08	0.97 ± 0.06
D-dimer, ng/ml	271.1±19.6*	321.6±21.3*#	242.1±20.5	196.2±22.7
Von Willebrand factor (VWF:AG), IU/ml	1.43±0.14*	1.68±0.12*	1.35±0.19*	0.78±0.11
C-reactive protein, g/L	14.8±4.4*	18.3±5.1*	8.3±4.7	4.5±3.1
AST, U/L	36.8±7.7*	45.4±7.3*#	28.1±6.9	21.5±5.2
ALT, U/L	39.3±8.1*	47.6±6.4*#	27.3±7.2	24.6±6.5

Notes: * - the difference is significant compared to the indicator of women in the control group (p<0.05).

- the difference is significant compared to the indicator of women in the O2 group (p<0.05).

Against the background of relative thrombocytopenia, an increase in ADP-induced platelet aggregation is observed (65.6±4.8% versus 50.2±5.8% in groups O1 and O2, p<0.05). The prothrombotic orientation of changes in the hemostasis system corresponds to a slight increase in fibrinogen content and an increase in the prothrombin index, a relative decrease in activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT).

The most pronounced changes in COVID-19 in pregnant women were noted for D-dimer, the highest values (in three patients more than 10,000 ng/ml) were recorded in group O1 (average level 321.6±21.3 versus 242.1±20.5 ng/ml in patients in group O2, p<0.05). In general, an increase in the indicator was observed in 42 (84.0%) pregnant women in group O1 and in 93 (62.0%) in group O2 (p<0.05). Violations of endothelial function in COVID-19 are evidenced by an increase in the level of von Willebrand factor as determined by its antigen (VWF:AG) to 1.43±0.14 versus

0.78±0.11 IU/ml in women in the main group relative to the control group, $p < 0.05$). Excessive inflammatory reaction causes destructive changes in various organs, in particular in the lungs and liver. A significant increase in transaminase levels was noted both in relation to the indicators of women in the control group and in patients in the group with perinatal losses in relation to the control and group O2. Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) was above the normative values in 110 (55.0%) women in the main group, of which 42 (84.0%) patients in group O1 and 68 (45.3%) in group O2 ($p < 0.05$). The level of aspartate aminotransferase (AST) was also significantly increased: above the norm in 40 (80.0%) patients in group O1 and in 66 (44.0%) in group O2 ($p < 0.05$).

The level of the inflammatory marker C-reactive protein was significantly increased in the main group in relation to the control group, and in group O1 its value was significantly higher in relation to the indicator in group O2 (18.3±5.1 versus 8.3±4.7 g/l, $p < 0.05$).

The severity of inflammatory processes directly correlates with the severity of the viral disease. Severe COVID-19 was recorded in a third of pregnant women (Fig. 1). At the same time, in group O1, such patients constituted the vast majority (66.0% versus 22.7% in group O2, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 1 Distribution of pregnant women with COVID-19 by severity of illness

The severity of COVID-19 disease may be indicated by an increase in inflammatory markers (Fig. 2).

The vast majority of patients had an elevated level (11 mg/l and above) of C-reactive protein (74.0%), with the frequency reaching 90.0% in group O1 (versus 68.7% in group O2, $p < 0.05$), significantly higher in subgroup O1 and the frequency of extremely high values (100 mg/l and above): 18.0% versus 4.7%, respectively ($p < 0.05$). High levels of the acute phase protein of inflammation – procalcitonin (0.1 ng/ml and above) were observed in 22.0% of patients with COVID-19, in particular in half of women in group O1 (versus 12.7% in group O2, $p < 0.05$). Such indicators indicate an acute inflammatory process, which can cause significant destructive changes in the body of patients in group O1, which leads to perinatal losses and disorders.

Many researchers have identified interleukin-6 as a marker of inflammation, immune dysfunction, and cytokine storm in COVID-19. According to our data, an increase in interleukin-6 (Fig. 3) was observed in 24.5% of patients in the main group, with 52.0% of such pregnant women in group O1 versus 15.3% in group O2 ($p < 0.05$). The much higher frequency of very high levels of this cytokine (50.0 mg/ml and above) in group O1 versus group O2 (10.0% versus 1.3%, $p < 0.05$)

is noteworthy.

Figure 2. Distribution of pregnant women with COVID-19 by level of inflammatory markers

Figure 3. Distribution of COVID-19 pregnant women by indexes of immunity

An important role in both gestational processes and antiviral protection is played by such an indicator of cellular immunity as NK-cytotoxicity, and its negative effect can be both a decrease (insufficient immune protection) and an increase (destructive effect on the body). According to our data (see Fig. 3.8), a decrease in the indicator (15% and below) was observed 4 times more often in group O1 compared to group O2 (12.0% vs. 2.7%, $p < 0.05$). A dangerous increase in NK-cytotoxicity was observed in almost every fifth patient in group O1 (24.0% vs. 6.7%, $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions

The inflammatory reaction of the body of pregnant women with COVID-19 and perinatal disorders is evidenced by leukocytosis and a shift in the blood formula to the left. Against the background of relative thrombocytopenia, an increase in ADP-induced platelet aggregation is observed ($65.6 \pm 4.8\%$ vs. $50.2 \pm 5.8\%$, $p < 0.05$), an increase in the level of D-dimer (321.6 ± 21.3 vs. 242.1 ± 20.5 ng/ml, $p < 0.05$).

Destructive changes in the liver are indicated by a significant increase in the level of

transaminases: ALT in 84.0% (vs. 45.3%, $p < 0.05$), AST in 80.0% of patients (vs. 44.0%, $p < 0.05$).

Severe COVID-19 was recorded in most patients (66.0% vs. 22.7%, $p < 0.05$), which is consistent with high levels of inflammatory markers: C-reactive protein (90.0% vs. 68.7%, $p < 0.05$), procalcitonin in half of the women (vs. 12.7%, $p < 0.05$), interleukin-6 (52.0% vs. 15.3%, $p < 0.05$), NK-cytotoxicity (24.0% vs. 6.7%, $p < 0.05$).

The high activity of inflammatory processes detected in COVID-19 in patients with perinatal disorders underlies systemic vasculitic changes and defects in blood coagulation processes, which cause damage to the maternal-fetal complex.

References/Література:

1. Aktas G. A comprehensive review on rational and effective treatment strategies against an invisible enemy; SARS Cov-2 infection. *Exp Biomed Res.* 2020;3(4):293–311. doi: 10.30714/J-EBR.2020463629.
2. Gündüz Ö, Seven B, Ozgu-Erdinc AS, Ayhan SG, Sahin D, Tekin OM, Keskin HL. Correlation of systemic inflammation biomarkers and disease severity in pregnant women with COVID-19. *Rev Assoc Med Bras (1992).* 2023 Jun 26;69(6):e20221614. doi: 10.1590/1806-9282.20221614. PMID: 37377284; PMCID: PMC10305815.
3. Vakili S, Savardashtaki A, Jamalnia S, Tabrizi R, Nematollahi MH, Jafarinia M, et al. Laboratory findings of COVID-19 infection are conflicting in different age groups and pregnant women: a literature review. *Arch Med Res.* 2020;51(7):603–607. doi: 10.1016/j.arcmed.2020.06.007.
4. Karimi A, Shobeiri P, Kulasinghe A, Rezaei N. Novel systemic inflammation markers to predict COVID-19 prognosis. *Front Immunol.* 2021;12:741061–741061. doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2021.741061.
5. Boushra MN, Koyfman A, Long B. COVID-19 in pregnancy and the puerperium: a review for emergency physicians. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2021;40:193–198. doi: 10.1016/j.ajem.2020.10.055.
6. Narang K, Enninga EAL, Gunaratne MDSK, Ibiroga ER, Trad ATA, Elrefaei A, et al. SARS-CoV-2 infection and COVID-19 during pregnancy: a multidisciplinary review. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2020;95(8):1750–1765. doi: 10.1016/j.mayocp.2020.05.011.
7. Westergaard D, Lundgaard AT, Vomstein K, et al. Immune changes in pregnancy: associations with pre-existing conditions and obstetrical complications at the 20th gestational week—a prospective cohort study. *BMC Med.* 2024 Dec 18;22(1):583. doi: 10.1186/s12916-024-03797-y. PMID: 39696496; PMCID: PMC11657209
8. Mor G, Aldo P, Alvero AB. The unique immunological and microbial aspects of pregnancy. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2017;17(8):469–482. doi: 10.1038/nri.2017.64.
9. Fois AG, Paliogiannis P, Scano V, Cau S, Babudieri S, Perra R, et al. The systemic inflammation index on admission predicts in-hospital mortality in COVID-19 patients. *Molecules.* 2020;25(23):5725–5725. doi: 10.3390/molecules25235725.
10. Berry M, Wang A, Clark SM, Harirah HM, Jain S, Olson GL, et al. Clinical stratification of pregnant COVID-19 patients based on severity: a single academic center experience. *Am J Perinatol.* 2021;38(5):515–522. doi: 10.1055/s-0041-1723761.
11. Foo SS, Cambou MC, Mok T, et al. The systemic inflammatory landscape of COVID-19 in pregnancy: Extensive serum proteomic profiling of mother-infant dyads with in utero SARS-CoV-2. *Cell Rep Med.* 2021 Nov 16;2(11):100453. doi: 10.1016/j.xcrm.2021.100453. Epub 2021 Oct 27. PMID: 34723226; PMCID: PMC8549189.

Author's contribution

Робота є одноосібною.

Фінансування

Це дослідження не отримало зовнішнього фінансування

Висновок комісії по біоетиці

Проведення дослідження затверджено етичним комітетом НУОЗ України імені П.Л. Шупика (Протокол № 3/24 від 22.03.2024)., дотримано основних морально-етичних

принципів Гельсінської декларації Всесвітньої медичної асоціації з біомедичних досліджень.

Заява про поінформовану згоду

Від пацієток було отримано письмову поінформовану згоду на обробку персональних даних та їх подальше використання.

Заява про доступність даних

Вся інформація знаходиться у відкритому доступі, дані щодо конкретного пацієнта можуть бути отримані на запит у автора.

Конфлікт інтересів

Автор заявляє про відсутність конфлікту інтересів

Використання штучного інтелекту.

ШІ не використовували під час написання даної роботи.

Робота надійшла в редакцію 02.06.2025 року.

Рекомендована до друку на засіданні редакційної колегії після рецензування